

**Repository to: Dual intracellular staining of CD154(CD40L) and cytokines at single cell level:
a novel aid to document immediate hypersensitivity to amoxicillin**

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Repository methods

Patients

As shown in [Repository table E1](#), Patients with a documented IDHR to AX were included. As recommended by the international guidelines ²⁷ and recently updated in EAACI position paper ²⁹, diagnosis was confirmed by positive immediately read STs and, if negative, quantification of sIgE and, if both STs and sIgE were negative, a positive graded DCT with AX ²⁹. Patients with suspected immediate AX hypersensitivity but with negative STs, sIgE and uneventful DCT with AX served as an exposed control group. Data from 5 uneventfully exposed controls were partially presented earlier ⁴.

Diagnostic testing

Skin testing

In parallel with our earlier studies on AX hypersensitivity ^{36, 43, 44}, STs with AX were performed according to the ENDA guidelines ⁴⁵ ([Repository table E2](#)). SPTs were read after 15 minutes and considered positive when the wheal and flare reaction exceeded 3 mm. Patients with negative SPTs had additional IDTs. IDTs were considered positive when the size of the wheal and flare reaction equalled or exceeded 5 mm within 20 minutes.

Quantification of total IgE and specific IgE antibodies

Total serum IgE (tIgE) and sIgE to penicilloyl G and/or penicilloyl V and/or ampicilloyl and/or amoxicilloyl antibodies were measured using a FEIA ImmunoCAP system (Phadia Thermo Fisher, Uppsala, Sweden). Results were considered positive when equalling or exceeding 0.35 kUA/L ^{27, 43}.

Drug challenge test (DCT)

Drug challenge tests are detailed elsewhere ⁴⁴. Briefly, all DCTs were performed in hospital environment under strict surveillance with access to emergency room facilities. Incremental doses of AX were administered in 3-steps. The up-dosing interval was predefined at 30 min. After the last dose, patients were kept under close observation for at least 2 hrs. A DCT was considered positive only when objective symptoms indicative for an IDHR were observed (e.g., hypotension, urticaria, angioedema, and wheezing). After DCTs, all participants had a follow-up visit to ensure they did not experience a NIDHR, as this would have excluded them from the current study.

T-lymphocyte activation test (LAT, intracellular (ic.-) CD154/IL-4/IFN- γ -LAT)

For the LAT, peripheral blood mononuclear cells were collected after a density gradient isolation with Histopaque (Merck, St. Louis, Missouri, USA). Each tube contains 2.10^6 cells in AIM-V medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific (TFS), Merelbeke, Belgium) with 2.5% decompemented autologous plasma. The experiment includes the AIM-V negative control and a positive control (Staphylococcus aureus enterotoxin B, Merck, St. Louis, Missouri, USA). After a preincubation of 2 hrs at 37°C 5% CO₂ and saturated humidity with anti-human CD28 (TFS, final concentration 5 μ g/mL), a protein transport inhibitor containing Brefeldin A (BD Biosciences, Erembodegem, Belgium) was added followed by AX (Sandoz, Vilvoorde, Belgium) in three concentrations (final concentration AX: 0.55, 1.37 and 2.74 mM). Subsequently, incubation at 37°C 5% CO₂ and saturated humidity for an additional 16 hrs was performed. After centrifugation, the cell pellet was resuspended in phosphate buffered saline (PBS pH = 7.4) containing 0.5% bovine serum albumin (BSA). Cells were stained with anti-human CD3-PerCP (BD Biosciences) and with the LIVE/DEAD™ Fixable Near-IR Dead Cell Stain Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) during 20 min at 4°C. After lysis and fixation with lysing solution (BD Biosciences) during 20 min at room temperature, cells were centrifuged and permeabilized with 0.3% saponin in PBS (Merck, St. Louis, Missouri, USA). Cells were stained with anti-human CD154-PE (BD Biosciences), anti-human IL-4-APC (BD Biosciences) and anti-human IFN- γ -BV421 (BD Biosciences) for 30 min at 4°C in the dark. Cells were washed in 0.3% saponin and resuspended in PBS for flow cytometric analysis at single cell level.

Flow cytometry

Flow cytometry was performed on a FACSCanto II™ flow cytometer (BD Immunocytometry Systems, San Jose, CA, USA) equipped with three lasers (405, 488, and 633 nm). Correct compensation settings for antibodies conjugated with fluorochromes were performed using BD™ CompBeads (BD Biosciences). Flow cytometric data was analyzed using Kaluza Analysis 2.1 software (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA) and FCS Express 7 Research edition (De Novo Software, Pasadena, CA, USA). A fluorescence minus one (FMO) was used to distinguish between positive and negative cells. Gating strategy is demonstrated in [repository figure E1](#). Note that this protocol is entirely identical to the method used to document NIDHRs to AX in our earlier study ³⁶, except for the additional and simultaneous staining for trapped IL-4 and IFN- γ . Representative plots are shown in [repository figure E2](#).

Repository tables and figures

Repository table E1. Demographics, symptoms, and outcomes of diagnostics in patients with an immediate hypersensitivity reaction to amoxicillin.

Patient	Sex	Age (y)	Drug involved in index reaction	Delay workup (weeks)	Symptoms	Diagnostic work-up AX		Delay experiments (weeks)
						ST	slgE	
1	F	58	AX	42	Immediate rash	+	-	0
2	F	27	AX/CL	1	Anaphylaxis	-	+	17
3	F	72	AX	Un	Anaphylaxis	-	+	865
4	F	32	AX/CL	7	Anaphylaxis	+	+	0
5	F	60	Undefined oral penicillin	Un	Angio-oedema	+	-	6
6	F	64	AX	8	Anaphylaxis	+	-	2
7	F	26	AX/CL	7	Urticaria, angio-oedema	+	-	3
8	F	63	Undefined oral penicillin	1	Immediate rash	+	-	1
9	F	40	AX	488	Urticaria, angio-oedema	-	+	23
10	M	49	Undefined oral penicillin	29	Immediate rash	+	-	5
11	F	62	Undefined oral penicillin	9	Immediate rash	+	-	3
12	F	59	AX	2162	Urticaria, angio-oedema	+	-	15
13	F	60	Undefined oral penicillin	19	Immediate rash	+	-	1
14	F	57	AX/CL	16	Urticaria, angio-oedema	+	+	5
15	M	33	AX/CL	7	Anaphylaxis	+	-	14

F = female; M = male; AX = amoxicillin; AX/CL = amoxicillin clavulanic acid; Un = unknown; ST = skin test; Age at moment of experiments. Delay workup = delay between index reaction and diagnostic workup; Delay experiments = delay between initial diagnostic workup and the T-lymphocyte activation test.

Repository table E2. Protocol for skin testing of amoxicillin or amoxicillin clavulanic acid

	Concentration
Skin prick test	0.2 mg/mL
	2 mg/mL
	20 mg/mL
Intradermal test	0.2 mg/mL
	2 mg/mL
	20 mg/mL

Histamine 10 mg/ml (ALKAbello, Hørsholm, Denmark) and isotonic sodium chloride were used as positive and negative controls respectively. For IDHRs, skin prick tests were read after 15 minutes and considered positive when the wheal of the wheal and flare reaction exceeded 3 mm. Patients with negative SPT had additional IDT. IDT responses were considered positive when the wheal of the wheal and flare reaction equalled or exceeded 5 mm.

Repository figure E1. Selection of CD3 positive T lymphocytes.

CD3⁺ T lymphocytes were selected based on single cell and live/dead selection.

Repository figure E2. Representative plots of the T-lymphocyte activation test

Stimulation with amoxicillin resulted in patient 1 in an upregulation of CD154 and IFN-γ while there is no upregulation of IL-4 compared to stimulation with buffer (negative control) or buffer and pre-incubated with anti-CD28. In contrast, patient 2 demonstrated almost no upregulation of CD154 and IFN-γ compared to stimulation with buffer (with and without anti-CD28 pre-stimulation) but showed a clear upregulation of IL-4.